

TRENDS OF URBAN SPREAD & ITS CHALLENGES: A STUDY ON ENGLISH BAZAR MUNICIPALITY

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Abstract: In India, a settlement gets the urban tag when it reaches a minimum population of 5000 with 75% of its population engaged in non-agricultural pursuits and a density of 400 persons per sq. k. m. An urban centre grows with time if it can create enough urban pull in the surrounding regions. In this pull the urban authority, e.g. a municipality or corporation, plays a major part. Its performance determines the livability of the urban centre and its future spread. With the urban spread come challenges of administering an ever growing population, providing required urban amenities and infrastructure, creating a sustainable urban economy, finding out problems and opportunities and planning for future. English Bazar is the district town of Malda district of West Bengal, originally developed by the British in the middle of the seventeenth century even before the district came up. The English Bazar Municipality came up in the year 1869. Since then it has come up as the second largest town in North Bengal. This study tries to go through the development of the town and its citizens, to analyze the performance of the municipality and the weaknesses and opportunities therein.

Keywords: Urban Spread, Amenities, Infrastructure, Development, Challenges

1. INTRODUCTION:

An urban area is that which is governed by a municipality, corporation, cantonment board or notified town area committee. Or it must have a minimum population of 5000 with 75% of it engaged in non-agricultural pursuits and a minimum density of 400 persons/ sq. k. m. The growth of the urban centre is very much dependant on the work of the municipality or corporation which runs it. A Municipality is a body, politic and legal entity, constituted by Statutory Act. Municipal Corporations constitute the highest or topmost form of urban local governments. They're created under State Municipal Laws. When a human settlement gets its urban nature, development of a municipality to administer it becomes eminent. On the other hand work of that municipality determines the future trend of spread of that urban centre.

The English Bazar Municipality is located in the Sadar sub-division of Malda district. The Municipality is located at 25°00'14" North Latitude and 88°11'20" East Longitude. River Mahananda flows along the eastern margin of the town. On its opposite bank lie Old Malda Block and Municipality. The original town was set up as a trade centre of indigo and silk, by the East India Company traders in the seventeenth century. The Municipality of English Bazar was formed on 1st of April 1869 with 5.53 sq. km. of land area. The town is well connected with rest of the district and state via NH 34, which runs along the middle of the town, State Highways and

railway tracks. The local rail station Malda Town is a divisional rail station of the Eastern railway. The town also has some attraction for tourism as it is closely located to the ruins of ancient capital of Bengal, Gour and Pandua.

Since independence urbanization in India is happening at an ever increasing rate. During the last decade (2001-11) urban population grew at a rate of 31.8%. Currently 31.16% (2011) of total population of the country lives in urban areas. Thus the study of the nature of spread and development of an urban centre is very much contemporary. But along with spatial expansion; changes in population characteristics, municipal infrastructure and amenities, livability and sustainability of the town needs to be analyzed. In this process the challenges in the path of development would come up and some opportunities could also be identified.

1.1. Study Area:

English Bazar is the district headquarters and biggest town in Malda district of West Bengal. Originally it was set up as a trade centre by the English traders in the seventeenth century to the west bank of river Mahananda. To the opposite bank was the older town of Mughal period, now known as Old Malda, at which the British had experienced troubles in doing business. So the new market, known as 'Engrezabad' or 'Nayahaat', came up around a British fortress, part of which presently houses the district court and other government offices. With time the population grew in size and started to take urban nature. Thus the requirement for an administrative body to govern and manage the town and its citizen increased. The Municipality of English Bazar was formed on 1st of April 1869 with 5.53 sq. km. of land area. In 1901, it had the total population of 13667 persons. From 1921, the population has regularly increased, with the rate being much greater after independence. At the time of independence the total population was 30663 (census, 1951) which now stands at 216083 (census, 2011) i.e. almost a seven times growth in a span of only 60 years. So has been the development of the town which has well connectivity with the rest of the state and the country via rail and road network, houses the district hospital, a university and other institutions for higher education and all the district offices of government and private institutions. The English Bazar Municipality itself is about to complete 150 years in 2019.

1.2. Objectives:

The following objectives have been set for the study:

- To assess the nature of urban spread, both from the aspects of area and population
- To analyze the public and municipal infrastructure, amenities and services
- To find out the shortcomings or weaknesses in the process of development and the opportunities therein.

2. METHODOLOGY:

2.1. Sample Design and Data Collection:

The study is based on data collected from both primary and secondary surveys. Secondary data have been collected from English Bazar Municipality, West Bengal State Electricity Development Corporation Ltd. (WBSEDCL), District Gazetteers, Census Report, District Statistical Hand Books (DSHB) and earlier writings about English Bazar and Malda. The primary data came from the household survey done in December, 2015 taking a total of 250 houses, 10 houses each from 25 wards. The questionnaire enlisted topics that aimed to find out peoples' perception regarding the infrastructures and services available in the town, e.g. road condition, water and electric supply, health and sanitation condition etc. It also covered the citizens' grievances if any and their suggestions.

2.2. Adoption of Statistical & Cartographic Techniques:

Both primary and secondary data have been analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively. Some statistical and cartographic techniques have been applied to represent the quantitative information. Shifting of Mean Centre method has been used to find out the direction of urban spread and population growth. Other statistical methods have been used to represent the development over time.

3. RESULTS & ANALYSIS:

3.1. Changes in Area and Structure:

Till independence there was no addition to the original 5.53 sq. km. area of English Bazar Municipality. At that time the municipality was divided into 4 wards from where 18 representatives for municipal governance were elected. In 1964 the municipal area was delimited into 14 wards and in 1968, in 18 wards. In 1985, another 8.1 sq. km. area was added to the English Bazar Municipality and it was divided into 24 wards. In the year 1995, ward no-24 was redistributed again in ward no. 24 and 25. Presently the municipality is distributed over 13.63 sq. km. of area and is divided into 25 wards. In between 2001 and 2011, there has been no addition to the area and also no changes in internal structure.

3.2. Changes in Demography:

• Population & its distribution:

The first census of India after independence (1951) estimated the total population to be 30663. So English Bazar was a class-III town at that time. It became a class-II town in 1971 when the total population became 61335 and a class-I town in 1991 when the total population was 139204.

According to census'2011 the total population of English Bazar has become 205521. It has always been a very densely populated town compared to other contemporary towns of Bengal. The population density is higher in old and core areas of the town which enjoy greater connectivity with market, hospital, bus stop, railway station and govt. offices etc.

Table 1: Changes in Area, Total Population and Population Density since Independence, E.B.M.

Year	Total Area (sq. km.)	Total Population	Density (persons/sq. km.)
1951	5.53	30663	5545
1971	5.53	61335	11091
1991	13.63	139204	10213
2011	13.63	205521	15078

Source: Census of India

Categorically S.C. and S.T. population in the town has always been very low compared to people from General category. The reserved category population appears to be living in few pockets of the town. Between 1991 and 2011, there hasn't been any significant change in this aspect.

Table 2: Caste wise distribution of Population (in %), E.B.M. (1991-2011)

Year	S.C.	S.T.	General
1991	10.81	0.92	88.27
2001	11.33	1.09	87.58
2011	9.61	1.23	89.16

Source: Census of India

The sex ratio in English Bazar has always been poor as any other urban centre of India. In 1951, it was only 876 females per thousand males. The value for 1991 and 2001 were 928 and 949 respectively. The sex ratio has again gone down to 924 in 2011 when the state figure stood at 947. This big fall in sex ratio in 2011 can be contributed to the alarming fall in child sex ratio in the town within the period 2001-11.

Table 3: Child Sex Ratio in E.B.M. (1991-2011)

Year	Child Sex Ratio (No. of girls per thousand boys in the 0-6 years age group)
1991	939
2001	962
2011	790

Source: Census of India

• Growth Rate and Shift in Mean Centre of Population:

Apart from the period 1911-1921, the total population in the town has always increased since the first census of India. Though the rate is very uneven, a relation may be established between the high growth rate and proximity of the town to international border of Bangladesh. The growth rate reached as high as 49.7% within the period 1951-61 when there was huge immigration of

people from erstwhile East Pakistan to West Bengal after independence of India. Though the highest growth rate of 64.7% was observed during the period 1981-1991, just after the independence of Bangladesh and another round of huge immigration from the 'other side'. The growth rate lowered to 15.98% in 2001 and again rose up to 33.83% in 2011 (while population growth rate in West Bengal fell from 17.77% to 13.98% within 2001-11). This latest rise can be attributed to the recent development in the fields of infrastructure, education and health within 2001 and 2011. A private engineering college came up in 2005; a river bridge has joined the adjacent Sahapur panchayet with the town in 2008; University of Gour Banga and Malda Medical College came up within 2009-10. All these facts have worked as 'pull factors' for people to settle in English Bazar.

The 'mean centre of population' in a region is that point around which people tend to settle in. Now the change in position of mean centre indicates, change in the preference of people about locations to live at. The direction of movement shows the places where the population growth has been the highest. Within the period 1991-2011 (after the last extension in area in 1985), the mean centre has shifted inwards from margins of ward no. 18 to the west and north-west direction. This means wards located to the west and north-west direction of ward no. 18, have experienced the highest population growth during this period. Now the highest population growth rates within 1991-2011 have been observed in newly added wards (1985) of 21, 22, 23, 24 and 25. The rate varied between 69%-131%. The reason behind this may be the cheaper land prices in those places compared to old core areas, availability of vacant plots, improvement in transport facilities and other civic amenities in those areas.

Table 4: Comparison in prices of flats (rupees per sq. feet) in E. B. M.

Location	Ward No.	Prices of 2BHK flats (Rupees/sq. feet)
Rabindra Avenue	VI	3500/-
Gour Road	VII	4000/-
Vivekananda Pally	XIX	3000/-
Station Road	XXIV	2750/-

Source: Primary Survey

• **Status of Literacy:**

The town of English Bazar always had the highest literacy rate in the district. In the year 1951, 47.9% of the population was literate. The value improved to 64.94% in 1991 and 72.38% in 2011 (while the state figure was 77.08%). Literacy rate has remained higher for men and higher in core areas.

• **Work Participation and categories of workers:**

The rate of work participation has always remained low. In the year 1991, the working population was 27.16% of total. The work participation rate improved to 30.54% in 2001 and 31.78% in 2011. The work participation rate for women has remained much lower in this period. It was only 6.46% in 1991, improved to 10.03% in 2001 and 13.01% in 2011. This shows that women empowerment hasn't been very high in the town. This may be blamed to low literacy rate among women, conservative society etc.

The urban nature of English Bazar is clearly evident from the fact that a very little amount of workers had remained associated with primary activities since the beginning. In 1951, only 5% of the population was engaged in primary sector. The value has lowered to 3.47% in 2011.

Table 5: Category wise distribution of workers (in %)

Categories of Workers	1991	2001	2011
Cultivators	1.00	0.41	0.64
Agricultural Labourers	1.09	0.52	0.45
Household Industry Workers	3.67	1.98	1.87
Other Workers	94.24	97.09	97.04
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: DSHB

3.3. Civic Amenities:

• Water Supply:

Ground water is the only source of drinking water and its use started in the year 1958. There's no filtering station. Underground water is lifted up via Deep Tube wells and supplied to households and street taps, using suction pipes. Sample testing of water is done at regular intervals at Kolkata laboratories to ensure its quality. There're 2 Over head reservoirs of 100000 gallon capacity and 50 Pump houses. In the year 2005, E. B. M. introduced Purified Water Tanks in each ward to supply filtered water inside the municipal area. They're of 2 types- a. Single Chamber Filters in the areas with less iron content in the ground water and b. Oxidised Double Chamber Filters in the areas with greater iron content.

Presently, 50 permanent and 44 temporary employees are working in the E.B.M. Dept. of Water Works. E. B. M. is collecting water tax at the following rate- Rs. 15/month per household and Rs. 150/month per commercial connection.

The municipality plans to set up a treatment plant that will fetch water from river Ganga near Farakka, next the water will be purified and supplied to the E. B. M. area. The E.B.M. also plans to withdraw Hydrants with more numbers of Purified Water Tanks.

Table 6: Daily Supply of Water, E.B.M. (1991-2011)

Year	Amount of Water (in Gallon)
1991	1200000
2001	2639631
2011	4267403

Source: Dept. of Water Works, E.B.M.

• Public Works:

The road density in the year 2001, varied between less than 6 to more than 30 km. per sq. km. among different wards. The road density in E.B.M. improved from 21.57 km. per sq. km. in 2001 to 28.45 km. per sq. km. in 2011. But this growth is far below than required with respect to the vehicular growth in the town.

The length of drains has improved from 295.32 km. in 1991 to 405.42 km. in 2011. More number of open surface drains is being converted to box surface drains. The sewage water opens up in River Mahananda and Bhatia Bil. There's no treatment plant to filter the sewage water. The municipality does not have any permanent dumping ground. Daily amount of garbage generation increased from 85 metric tons in 1991 to 210 metric tons in 2011. The number of cleaning personnel employed by municipality in this period increased from 125 to 290. The municipality spreads D.D.T., larvicide oil with adulticide using fogging machine to resist mosquito borne diseases. The E.B.M. gives subsidy to B.P.L. families to build up latrines in their homes. The municipality uses hand carts, trolleys and container carrier system for collecting and dumping garbage.

The municipality plans to introduce Measure for Solid Waste Management System to treat organic and inorganic waste separately. They plan to develop Treatment Plant to separate pollutants from sewage water.

Table 7: Grievances of citizens in E.B.M. regarding waste disposal and cleaning operations

Types of Grievances	% of Respondents
Irregular cleaning of garbage from dustbins and sewage lines	39
Irregular spraying of mosquito repellants, insecticides etc.	30
Water logging in sewage lines	7
No Problem	24

Source: Primary Survey

The E.B.M. has been taking care of street electrification since 1985. More number of tube sets and vapor lamps are being introduced now to replace old 40/60 watts lamps and halogens. In the year 2010, E.B.M started building High Mass Towers at important crossings of roads. They're now 9 in numbers, each one having 6 metal sets of 400 watts. More towers are to come in future and more energy efficient options are to be introduced.

• **Health Facilities:**

The Dept. of Health, Govt. of West Bengal runs Sadar Hospital, Police Hospital, Leprosy and T.B. hospitals inside the municipality. There's also a railway hospital run by Indian Rail. Now a government medical college has started operating in the Sadar Hospital Campus. It is expected to lift up the medical scenario of the district.

E.B.M. operated Matri Sadan maternity hall is completely for women. E.B.M. also operates 2 Health Posts one of which is homoeopathic and the other is Bio-chemic Health Centre. There're also 14 Sub-Health Posts distributed over the town.

On the other hand, a number of Nursing homes, Poly-clinics, Pathology Centre etc. are operating inside the town. They offer different facilities like C.T. Scan, Ultra-sonography, X-Ray, E.C.G, Halter Monitoring, Audiometry, E.E.G., Radiography, Pulmonary Function Test, Bio-chemistry, Hematology, Rheumatology, Bone marrow, Histopathology etc.

• **Electric Supply:**

In earlier days a huge generator was used to supply electricity for street electrification, offices and houses of influential people. Now electric is transmitted from 3 substations; operated by W.B.S.E.T.C.L, namely-

1. Ghorapir 132/33/11 KVA substation
2. Kalindi 33/11 KVA substation
3. Rabindra Bhawan 33/11 KVA substation (built up in 2001)

W.B.S.E.D.C.L. distributes the energy via transformers dividing the town into Rathbari, Fulbari and Makdumpur sectors.

Table 8: Infrastructure and Use of electricity in E.B.M. (2007-11)

Year	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011
Total no. of Transformers	459	528	554	620	642
Total no. of Consumers	56095	53514	61977	66899	69632
Total Electric Supply (mu)	78457	84903	94721	100121	111743

Source: WBSEDCL

• **Other Services:**

The District Police Headquarter, English Bazar Police Station and 2 police outposts are there inside the municipality.

English Bazar Fire Station is also located in the municipality. It is a 'two-pump' station operating under W.B. Fire and Emergency Services, serves public under emergencies like fire, emergency rescue etc. In the year 2011, it had 30 personnel.

Table 9: Available fire appliances, English Bazar Fire Station, 2011

Mounted Pump	2	Utility Van	1
Water Bourse	1	Portable Pump	3
Trailer Van	1	Trailer Pump	1

Source: Primary Survey

3.4 Economy:

E.B.M. had a deficit budget in the year 1991 with municipal expenditure being greater than the receipt. However a surplus was observed in budget 2001 which can be blamed to factors like introduction of water tax, more tax collection etc. The budget for 2015 gives equal amount in receipt and expenditure. The sources of receipts are- tax collection, revenue from power and property and Govt. grant. While expenditure are done in fields of administration, public safety, public health and convenience, public works public institutions and others.

There's no large scale industry within the town. Among the products manufactured in household and cottage industries, silk fabrics come first followed by mango products and mustard oil. Again the major commodities to be exported are- mango, silk and fish.

4. FINDINGS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS:

High density and high population growth rate has increased the demand and in turn the price of land in the town. The land price in few areas is comparable to the suburbs of city of Kolkata.

Residential flats are coming up rapidly in place of old, single family dwellings.

Built up areas are rapidly encroaching vacant spaces. Green is fading in the town.

Another trend has been observed that poor families are selling off their land properties inside E.B.M. for money and are opting to settle at adjacent areas of Old Malda Municipality, Sahapur Panchayet etc.

The population is growing rapidly in last added areas of ward- 21, 22, 23, 24 and 25. But civic infrastructures are still insufficient there. The proportions of non-metalled roads, open surface drains and problems of insufficient street lights, irregular waste collection etc. is more in these wards.

The growth in human and vehicle population has been much greater than growth in road length in the last decade (2001-11). More number of private vehicles has taken the road in recent years, e-rickshaws have encroached lanes and by-lanes of the town, footpaths have been encroached by the street hawkers; the safety of the pedestrians is at stake. There has been a recent spurt in road accidents in the town. The authority has to look for road widening and lengthening options for better traffic management and road safety.

Citizens have complained about higher iron content in water supplied by the municipality. Arsenic contamination has been observed in water samples from some areas of the municipality. The municipality has to fasten their project of supplying purified drinking water from river Ganga.

No dumping ground for waste disposal has been one of the biggest challenges for E.B.M. Unrestrained dumping of garbage here and there affects the environment severely. E.B.M. has to introduce the solid waste management system and sewage water treatment plant soon. Opening of the sewage lines in river Mahananda has already polluted the water severely.

The town has huge potential for becoming a medical hub. People from all over the district, surrounding districts and even from Bangladesh come here in English Bazar for medical purposes. There are huge numbers of specialized doctors, clinics with modern treatment facilities etc. The establishment of Malda Medical College has further improved the scenario.

The closeness to ancient capitals of Bengal- Gour and Pandua, has created huge potential for tourism in the town. But the poor connectivity and transport facilities to these places, poor conditions of the spots and absence of organized tours have not allowed realization of this tourism potential. Care should be taken in this regard.

REFERENCES:

- Allen B.C., Gait E.A., Allen C.G.H., Howard H.F (1979): Gazetteer of Bengal and North-East India, (Reprint) Mittal Publications, Delhi.
- Carter M.O (1938): Final Report on the Survey and Settlement Operation in the District of Malda 1928-1935, N. L. Publishers (Reprint 1993), Siliguri, West Bengal.
- Govt. of India (2011): Census of India 1951, 1971, 1991, 2001, 2011, Department of Census Operations, Kolkata.
- Govt. of India (1991): District Census Hand Book 1991, Department of Census Operations, Kolkata.
- Govt. of West Bengal, District Statistical Hand Book 2001, 2011, 2015, Bureau of Statistics, Kolkata.
- Ghosh R. G (2001): Ingraj Bazar Poursabhar Itibritto, R.K Publishing House, Maldah.
- Hunter W.W (1978): A Statistical Account of Bengal, Volume-VII: Malda, Rangpur and Dinajpur; D K Publishing House, Delhi

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আশিস অধিকারী ব্রজাঙ্গনা কাব্যে পৌরাণিক ভাবনা	২৪৭
সুদীপ্ত প্রামাণিক বিনয় মজুমদার : কবিতা প্রক্রিয়া	২৫৩
রাতুল ঘোষ পশ্চিমবঙ্গের স্বাধীনোত্তর সংস্কৃত কবি-সম্প্রদায়	২৫৭
অভিজিৎ রায় ধর্মের মূলতত্ত্ব ও বর্তমানে তার প্রাসঙ্গিকতা	২৬৩
দূর্বাদল মন্ডল পাণ্ডবজনমের কাব্যিক ও দার্শনিক দিক :	২৬৭
কল্যাণ পণ্ডা বিজ্ঞানসম্মত ভাষা সংস্কৃত :	
তথ্যপ্রযুক্তিতে তার প্রাসঙ্গিকতা	২৭২
অরূপ দাস	